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“SIERRA MADRE: THE LIFELINE OF TOMORROW”

With its longest ranges, the mighty Sierra Madre rises high,
A mother to Luzon, a steadfast curator beneath the sky.
Its spine of stone, firm, fierce, and bold,
A sacred place, where power and tranquility unfold.

Roots deeply entwined with the earth, cradling the island in a watchful keep
The stream of the rivers, and halitus of trees
Absorbing floods, easing strain, taming storm, guarding land from pain
keeper of the New Castile and a shield of life against the rain.

Yet greedy eyes are blind, ravage her veins with hearts unkind
With every tree that meets the ground, the rivers shrink, no life resounds.
Leaving a deep scar, the earth whine dry,
A sorrowful echo of grief, a silent supplication beneath the sky.

From a forest deep flourished with green, Kaliwa Dam upheaval the scene
The miners' drills, a relentless, rumbling sound,
As precious minerals are ripped from sacred ground
The wildlife's cries, habitats shrivel on the holy ground

A mountain range which reflects resiliency,
Let ears hears its mournful entreaty, projects may be laid, yet let forest be,
Arise with dauntless hearts, our protector calls for a knight
Guard that longest range, let the mighty Sierra Madre continue to rise high.